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Post Conflict Rehabilitation in Post Gukurahundi Zimbabwe: The Role of Civil Society Institutions

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Abstract

Three decades after the Gukurahundi massacres, Zimbabwe has been marked by a disintegrated social fabric and cyclical ethnic tensions within Zimbabwean structures. As such, one may question the efficiency and viability of the national structures and the existence of a robust civil society, since peacebuilding initiatives ought to be a mandate reserved for civil society organizations (CSOs). It is within this stream of thought that one may grapple with the question, “Does Zimbabwe have the robust civil society machinery to pull off post-conflict initiatives?” This paper scrutinizes CSO-led post-conflict rehabilitation initiatives in their many facets, exploring their modus operandi as well as their efficacy in the post-Gukurahundi Zimbabwean context. Post-conflict reconstruction (PCR) is a vital building block in the quest for effective peacebuilding. This paper aims identify and evaluate these post-conflict efforts, and affirm them as a preventative measure against relapse into conflicts with the same dynamics. As such, post-conflict mechanisms employed by CSOs are scrutinized to determine their effectiveness and efficiency towards the attainment of sustainable peace. Nevertheless, CSOs in their quest for post-conflict peacebuilding

have been compromised by a myriad of factors ranging from CSO composition to State-CSO relations among others. In light of the argument presented in this work, recommendations are proposed in a bid to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of institutions and initiatives in question.

POST CONFLICT REHABILITATION IN POST GUKURAHUNDI ZIMBABWE: THE ROLE OF CIVIL SOCIETY INSTITUTIONS

Introduction

The Zimbabwean socio-political frame has been tainted by ethnic disparities birthed by the infamous Gukurahundi massacres of the 1980s. As a result, reconciliation and co-existence between the warring extremes remains unattainable in this region. This trend outlines the cyclical nature of deep-rooted conflicts, suggesting the need to establish institutions to break the destructive cycle. In a bid to rehabilitate affected societies, the government and civil society organizations (CSOs) have implemented various measures, strategies, and peacebuilding initiatives in an attempt to restore, heal, and reconcile affected societies and individuals. Furthermore, a plethora of civil society organizations such as IBhetshu Lika Zulu, Habakkuk Trust, Grace to Heal, Mthwakazi kaZulu (now Mthwakazi Republic Party), among other notable civil society institutions have also had their fair share of rehabilitation initiatives.

Nevertheless, the tribal brawl continues to intensify despite rehabilitation efforts by both state and non-state actors as the two ethnic groups—the Shona and the Ndebele—are still in a tug of war over past injustices. Given the current state of affairs, it is justified to state that Zimbabwe is sitting on a potential time bomb, as tribal and ethnic hostilities are bound to relapse into full-blown hostility; hence, post-conflict peacebuilding becomes a necessary remedy. This paper will unpack and evaluate the effectiveness of the post-conflict rehabilitation efforts pioneered by civil society organizations in the aftermath of the Gukurahundi genocidal massacres.

Historical Background

In the dawn of Zimbabwean Independence in 1983, civil strife broke out in Bulawayo, Matabeleland and the Midlands provinces respectively, such that 1983–1987 has been termed the African version of the Reign of Terror (Ndlovu-Gatsheni, 2008). In the aftermath of the War of Liberation, ZAPU militants failed to acknowledge and pledge allegiance to the elected regime (Murambadoro, 2015). Bloomfield (2003) concurs with Murambadoro that ethnic tensions between ZANU and ZIPRA forces resulted in suspicions of a coup by ZIPRA forces, which ultimately gave way to the civil strife. The alleged “dissidents” were of Ndebele descent, which is important to note. The government reacted by unleashing the Shona-concentrated Fifth Brigade which was to carry out “Gukurahundi.” Gukurahundi is a traditional Shona term meaning, “the early rains that wash away of the chaff before spring rains” (Moyo, 2012, cited in Murambadoro 2015, p. 37).

From a critical point of view, one might argue that the term Gukurahundi metaphorically suggested the wiping out of the Ndebele minority in order to establish a tribally biased one party state. Sokwanele (2007) affirms that the aim of Gukurahundi was to crush the people of Matabeleland and force them to submit to the new regime. As such, the Gukurahundi operation indirectly culminated in tribal hostility. As a result of this tribal brawl, crimes against humanity were unleashed by the Fifth Brigade not only on the alleged dissidents but also on civilians in the Matabeleland and Midlands regions. Consequently, the terror led to the loss of over 20,000 lives, unexplained disappearances, abductions, rapes and other dehumanizing acts, disintegrated families, disabled persons, internal displacement, and desire for vengeance and psychological trauma (Murambadoro, 2015).

In 1987, the government attempted to address these issues by signing the unity accord. In addition, presidential amnesty was granted to all of the so-called dissidents as a stepping-stone towards healing a fractured society. Nevertheless, these governmental attempts failed to yield intended results, which can be mainly attributed to the government and other civil society institutions using the wrong approach. Be that as it may, this angle of criticism ought to justify the Lederachian perspective considered in this paper.

Theoretical Framework

Lederachian Theory of Peacebuilding

This study is premised on the Lederachian Peacebuilding Pyramid proposed by John Paul Lederach (1997) in his publication *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*. Lederach's theory builds on the assumption that peacebuilding is a process, not an event. The Lederachian framework identifies key actors within the peacebuilding process, aligning them to respective transformative initiatives. Moreover, Lederach (1997) proposes that the peacebuilding process can be deployed as a bottom-up approach or a top-down approach, according to the preferences of the actor. In either case, the framework describes a symbiotic relationship between levels to ensure a comprehensive and sustainable peacebuilding process.

In the light of this peacebuilding framework, one may argue that the triple stratification of Lederach's pyramid ultimately promotes inclusiveness and comprehensiveness in the implementation of peacebuilding initiatives in a given context. Gutura (2015) concurs and appreciates the stratification of the pyramid, suggesting that peacebuilding initiatives manifest themselves on three levels. As a result of its holistic nature, inclusive and sustainable strategy, and propensity to positively influence the peacebuilding process, this approach has been termed a "comprehensive peacebuilding framework" (Gutura 2015). Furthermore, the multi-level peacebuilding pyramid promotes multi-level stakeholder participation, grassroots empowerment, and renders the post-conflict peacebuilding a joint effort (Dube and Makwerere, 2012). Lederach (1997) separates the three levels into actors and approaches, thereby identifying responsible

leaders and initiatives per suggested level, giving peacebuilding a stratified structure as described below.

This paper is theorized in terms of the Lederachian perspective as a means of investigating the extent to which the civil society organizations in question conform to the Lederachian perspective of peacebuilding in post-conflict initiatives. From a critical point of view, one may contend that the quality of a CSO initiative can be measured by its conformity to the Lederachian school of thought.

Lederach (1997) describes level one as the elitist level, as it is largely comprised of top-level leadership including the top clergy, heads of state, and the military; as such, they are viewed as iconic figures that tread the diplomatic route towards peacebuilding through use of power and influence (Gutura, 2015). The first level approach to peacebuilding is dominated by diplomatic initiatives such as shuttle mediations, negotiations, round table meetings, and negotiated ceasefires which ultimately give birth to peace accords and agreements which have insignificant impact on the lower levels, thus questioning the credibility of this top-to-bottom or trickle-down approach (Lederach, 1997). An example of level one peacebuilding was the signing of the Unity Accord in 1987 by the two iconic elites, which failed to positively impact the situation on the ground. One might argue that top-level peacebuilding initiatives are more symbolic than practical.

Level two is composed of CSOs, academics, and religious leaders such as bishops and pastors. This is an influential level, as actors in this segment have the capacity to positively influence both the first level and third level. Furthermore, Gutura (2015) posits that second-level actors tend to challenge the actions of top leadership; thus, they can be termed the “watchdogs,” as they perform checks and balances on both lower and higher levels. Middle-track approaches mainly focus on capacity building through problem solving initiatives and providing a platform for adversarial parties to converse. In the same light, Dube and Makwerere (2012) contend that the Lederachian school of thought is rooted in constructive social change that seeks to positively change the flow of human interaction. Level two actors serve as intermediaries between the grassroots and elites. For this reason, one may contend that they pioneer the bottom-up approach to peacebuilding by proving the necessary channels and infrastructure for peacebuilding (Lederach, 1997).

The base of the pyramid represents the third level of peacebuilding, known as the grassroots level. This level comprises both direct and indirect victims (Gutura 2015). Lederach (1997) opines that this level’s initiatives are victim centered, as they focus on trauma healing, psychosocial work, and prejudice reduction. Moreover, Lederach (1997) posits that grassroots initiatives are spearheaded by local community leaders as well as community-based organizations who are credible leadership to the grassroots, which comprises civilians affected by the conflict (Gutura, 2015). Within the same loop, community leader involvement ought to become a call for CSOs to collaborate and engage with community leaders if their initiatives are to be effective. Moreover, in a bid to rehabilitate the affected members of the community, level three spearheads initiatives around

healing long-standing traumas and addresses a deep-rooted sense of past injustices, as asserted by Dube and Makwerere in Musorowegomo (2013).

Furthermore, Lederach posits the importance of collaboration in peacebuilding, with initiatives implemented simultaneously across all levels. Guzura and Dube (2016) concur with Lederach as they postulate that peace processes cannot be achieved in isolation if they are to be transformative and sustainable, suggesting that there should be synergy among the three levels.

From Lederach's viewpoint, effective peacebuilding is hierarchical, and all three levels are interdependent and work in tandem. In this regard, one should be cognizant of the fact that among the three actors identified by Lederach (1997), the middle track actors are the life lifeline of post-conflict peacebuilding, as they become an adhesive between the apex and the base of the pyramid. Hence, the role of middle track, particularly CSOs, cannot be understated as far as post conflict rehabilitation and reintegration are concerned.

Lederach's theory is the epicenter of this paper, as its approach is congruent with the requirements of the study as well as the multi-faceted approach post-conflict processes. It outlines necessary and contextual approaches to post conflict peacebuilding and becomes a blueprint for peace practitioners to identify and prescribe viable and effective actions. Notably, the bulk of CSOs fall into the middle and third level brackets. As such, CSO initiatives in tandem with the first and third level actions offer a comprehensive and sustainable approach to peacebuilding.

Conceptual Framework

Peacebuilding

The concept of peacebuilding has been highly contested in the field of peace studies; however, Musorowegomo (2013) excavates its origins stating that Johan Galtung coined the term in his prominent works on peace. Galtung (1998) cited in Cardenas (2013) defines the notion of peacebuilding in his 3R model, which includes reconstruction, reconciliation and resolution. From Galtung's point of view, sustainable and holistic peacebuilding is achievable only if it seeks to reconstruct structures and mend altered relationships, as well as resolve pending disputes and irregularities. Embracing this comprehensive approach becomes a challenge for CSOs, and one may evaluate the extent to which they have used this approach in their operations in the post-Gukurahundi context.

Lederach (1997) conceptualizes peacebuilding in terms of human relations. He centers on reconciliation thus prioritizing human capital in peace processes. Ghali (1992) focuses on post-conflict peacebuilding and advocates for the strengthening of structures toward effective peacebuilding. One may contend that Ghali's concept of peacebuilding is rooted in the first and second levels of Lederach's pyramid. Moreover, it ultimately becomes the role of CSOs influence structures and policymaking.

Post-Conflict Rehabilitation

The term *post-conflict rehabilitation* is the jugular vein of this particular discussion, such that its conceptualization and understanding ultimately cements the study. Pugh (1998) posits that post-conflict rehabilitation encompasses a wide range of activities from social work, human rights monitoring, and reintegration as stepping stones in the transition from conflict to relative peace. Therefore, post-conflict rehabilitation and processes are mostly rooted in advocacy and social integration, which are arguably functions of a large number of CSOs. As such, CSOs should be the main actors, as most post-conflict requirements outlined by Pugh fall within the bracket of CSO functions.

Civil Society

In exploring the concept of civil society, Merkel and Lauth cited in Paffenholz and Spurk (2006) posit that civil society ought to be considered a voluntary platform, which is not influenced by the state. Instead, it is the CSO that influences the state through the provisions of checks and balances. Moreover, it should be considered that civil societies are built on values and shared interests. The CSOs under scrutiny here share mutual ground in post-conflict peacebuilding. Paffenholz and Spurk (2006) conceptualize civil society in terms of its functions, as suggested by the Merkel and Lauth Function Model, centering on the role of civil society in civilian protection, intermediary duties between state and civilians, socialization and social integration, community building, as well as facilitating communication processes between adversarial groups. Hence, in their peacebuilding quests, CSOs ought to fulfill the above-mentioned functions to ensure the success and effectiveness of their initiatives.

Civil Society in Post-Conflict Rehabilitation

Over the years, there has been a blurred distinction in regard to which institution is mandated to implement and oversee post-conflict rehabilitation (PCR) and peacebuilding initiatives: governmental institutions or the civil society. Presented with such a conundrum, this paper advocates the notion that CSOs are the sole institutions mandated to dominate the post-conflict arena. Moreover, this argument is further cemented by the Merkel and Lauth model, which stipulates and prescribes CSO operations.

Still, the civil society's years of activity in post-Gukurahundi peacebuilding are subject to scrutiny as most CSOs commenced their activities from early 2000s to the present. During the 1990s, the number of CSOs actively involved was limited to the Catholic Commission for Justice and Peace (CCJP). Habakkuk Trust stated that for the past three decades, the government imposed an unofficial ban on the Gukurahundi issue, which had an adverse effect of post-Gukurahundi peacebuilding efforts and ultimately contributed to a limited number of actors in this field. Thus, CSO-pioneered, post-conflict initiatives gained momentum almost two decades after the atrocities. This contradicts Paffenholz and Spurk (2006) who postulate that effective post-conflict processes

should be implemented 1–10 years after the conflict. As such, one may argue that the inability of CSOs to collectively implement post-conflict initiatives during the early stages of transition as suggested by Paffenholz (2006) ought to be held at ransom for the prevailing ethnic tensions. Further, this has immensely contributed to the recurrence of violent tendencies in Zimbabwe. CSOs such as the Ecumenical Church Leaders Forum (ECLF) are of the belief that post-conflict initiatives can be applied at any period of transition without any time limit attached to them there by justifying the time frame. Within the same stream of argument, Rev. Cele of ECLF stated in an interview,

As far as timeframe for PCR is concerned, I will refer to World War I atrocities perpetrated by Germany which are several decades old, but the implications still live on. As such post conflict rehabilitation has no time frame, but it just heals as far as the memory can reach.”

On another striking note, when one is working with the idea of civil society within this given context, it is of paramount importance to appreciate both sides of civil society namely the faith-based arm as well as the non-faith based arm of a CSO. The majority of CSOs engaged in post-Gukurahundi rehabilitation processes were faith-based organizations (FBOs), thus the role of these FBOs is usually understated (World Bank, 2006). FBOs such as Grace to Heal, Habakkuk Trust, and ECLF, as well as the CCJP were earmarked for post-conflict rehabilitation initiatives. Berchovith (2008) posits that the credibility and role of FBOs and religious institutions remains undisputable in spheres of conflict transformation, thereby making them perfect candidates for PCR. However, it is imperative to note that FBOs tend to be more concerned with issues of human security, social integration, and social cohesion as postulated by Katunga (2008). In a bid to complement Katunga’s postulation, faith-based institutions tend to be socially acceptable on moral and ethical grounds as they are bound by a sense of social responsibility; hence, their initiatives are bound to be better appreciated and promote social/local ownership of these post-conflict initiatives. Hence, faith-based are considered the custodians of a peaceful society, thus they fulfill their societal obligations through post-conflict initiatives. Nevertheless, to ensure a comprehensive approach in this discourse, non-faith based institutions’ initiatives are integrated in this paper and are scrutinized in a like manner.

CSO Post-Gukurahundi Initiatives and Strategies

Faith-Based Organization Initiatives

Within the 1990–2017 time frame, various CSOs have embarked on a number of post-conflict missions, some of which are still under way. These can be argued to have an inclination towards the transitional approach, as they are mostly restorative, rehabilitative, as well as therapeutic, and these include truth telling, dialoguing, advocacy and so on. This paper equally explores faith-based organization and non-faith based organization initiatives respectively, thereby embracing the multi-stakeholder and inclusive approach. In the same vein, one ought to appreciate the notion that non-FBOs tend to build their momentum from social sentiments as a mobilization tool to anchor

their initiatives. On the other hand, FBOs tend to speak truth to power. Thus, FBOs are considered the more effective institutions in the peacebuilding process. Nonetheless, both FBOs and non-FBOs have proven to be effective and efficient, as they conform to the Merkel and Lauth model as well as the Lederachian perspective.

Truth Telling and Healing

Healing and truth telling seem to dominate the post-conflict rehabilitation strategies implemented by CSOs. Murambadoro (2015) and Lederach (1997) concur that truth telling lays a firm foundation for dialogue and platform for reconciliation. It anchors rehabilitation and ultimately justifies the popularity of the strategy among CSOs. From an economic point of view, healing and truth telling are common as they require less or no monetary funds, hence the domination of these twin strategies within CSOs is justified on the basis of economics and cost efficiency. However, from a transitional approach adopted by ECLF, the two strategies/concepts have a symbiotic relationship, as one cannot exist outside the sphere of another. One cannot be a standalone concept without the other: there can be no healing (psychological, emotional) without truth telling; and there can be little to no chance of truth telling if healing has not taken place.

ECLF further defines healing not only in psychological and emotional terms but points out infrastructural development as a form of relevant healing that is contextual to the Bulawayo and Matabeleland regions. Devolution of power is one of the means to achieve this “specific type of healing” such that educational facilities are constructed for the affected areas to cater to their felt needs. In an interview, Cele of ECLF stated, “Government policies must be deliberate in promoting and developing people of the affected areas who are still dealing with Gukurahundi effects as well as cater for their contextual needs.”

Thus, healing is a multi-faceted approach that should be tackled from all angles to prevent the recurrence of conflicts with the same dynamics. Hence, it becomes a challenge for CSOs to spearhead such initiatives and not to limit their scope.

Local Peace Committees

Local Peace Committees (LPCs) are a stepping-stone towards promoting post-conflict peacebuilding at the grassroots level as a duty initiated by relevant CSOs (Lederach, 1997). From this standpoint, one is compelled to argue that ECLF is the main actor behind the implementation and formation of LPCs, as they have managed to adopt the bottom-up approach in post-conflict peacebuilding as prescribed by Lederach (1997), through the empowerment of grassroots and victims of atrocities. Thus, it can be argued that in order to create a strong foundation for durable peace, a transitional approach ought to be adopted to conform to the Lederachian perspective of peacebuilding.

Habakkuk Trust embarks on capacity-building initiatives, which, in this paper, will be classified as LPCs, as they focus on grassroots empowerment, especially victims. Nevertheless, one should

be cognizant of the fact that few CSOs embark on grassroots initiatives, as the majority of the CSOs have adopted the top-down approach, contributing to the ultimate failure of their initiatives. For CSO initiatives to be effective and efficient, they should embark on the bottom-up approach instead of the top-down approach.

Advocacy

Advocacy initiatives are mostly pioneered by Habakkuk Trust as per data generated for the purposes of this paper; however, it seems this strategy remains popular with other members of the CSO body. An advocacy approach ought to be applauded for its conformity to the Merkel and Lauth functional model, as it pioneers advocacy work within its operations. One may contend that the CSOs will ultimately become the voice of the victims, which seek to bring about social justice as postulated by World Bank (2006). Moreover, in the course of the study, it was excavated that through advocacy work, CSOs ultimately become the conscience of communities. As stated by one of the Bulawayo Metropolitan community leaders the Bulawayo Metropolitan Province Mayor in an interview, “Civil Society emerges to express a voice of the general populace pertaining to issues that affect them, and as such it becomes the conscience of the communities in question.”

Lederach (1997) delegates the middle track (i.e., the CSO) with the duty of conducting problem-solving workshops, which one may equate to the advocacy work performed by Habakkuk Trust. The conformity of Habakkuk Trust to the Lederachian pyramid authenticates advocacy as a viable post-conflict mechanism.

Taking a paradigm shift, non-faith based organizations have shared the limelight with their faith-based counterparts in engaging in advocacy work under the banner of post-conflict rehabilitation in the context of Gukurahundi. Typical of such organizations which have been the voice of Gukurahundi victims include, Mthwakazi Group, a pressure group which has turned political. At the dawn of the ceremonial February 21 movement earlier this year, the group aired concerns over the inappropriateness of the location, stating, “We cannot allow ZANU PF to hold a party near Bhalagwe (Matobo) Gukurahundi mass graves, to us it seems as a celebration of the atrocities” (*Bulawayo 24 News*). Still on the note of advocacy work, *Newsday Zimbabwe* reports civil society groups and opposition political parties have opened fire in response to the remarks by the home affairs minister that Gukurahundi was a non-issue. CSOs such as Mthwakazi Republic Party, ZAPU as well as IBhetshu Lika Zulu took up the task to address the alleged offender ZANU PF stating that they were being “irresponsible” as well as suggesting that ZANU as the offender should stop dodging accountability since “brushing a genocidal crime aside by making it a non-issue will not make it go away” (“Chombo Rapped,” 2017). Therefore, it goes without saying that these CSOs have been instrumental in advocacy work, as the voice of the voiceless stipulated in the Merkel and Lauth model. One may contend that CSOs have ultimately become the voice of the victims seeking to bring about social justice (World Bank 2006).

Within the discussion of CSO advocacy roles, it is imperative to note that the majority of CSOs

have been actively advocating for issuing of proper identification documentation to both the living and the dead, such as birth certificates and death certificates, as well as for the economic empowerment of both direct and indirect victims. It is therefore in this line of thought that the advocacy role of CSOs ought to be applauded. Taking a paradigm shift as far as advocacy is concerned, it is equally imperative to consider possible downsides of this approach due to massive political party involvement. From a critical point of view, one ought to be justified in stating that the Gukurahundi issue is currently exposed to the danger of being manipulated as a campaign strategy by politically ambitious individuals turning them “ethnic-entrepreneurs,” thereby compromising the entire post-conflict operation.

Dialoguing

CSOs such as Grace to Heal have managed to pioneer storytelling mechanisms which has therapeutic value to victims. Lederach (1997) submits that human interactions through dialoguing mend fractured relations, thereby setting the bar high for dialoguing as a viable bridge between the warring parties. In scrutinizing the delegated role of CSOs under the Lederachian perspective, Dube and Makwerere (2012) contend that CSOs ought to facilitate constructive social change through the flow of human interaction, which in this case can be justified as dialoguing. In the light of the above above-mentioned schools of thought, dialoguing is a viable instrument for social cohesion in divided societies such that its application in post conflict societies is justified.

Major drawbacks affecting the full-scale initiation of dialogue mechanisms include the lack of co-operation from the government as outlined by Habakkuk Trust. This fault line is evidence of the inability to conform to the Lederachian perspective, which advocates for co-operation amongst the three levels of the pyramid as advocated for by Guzura and Dube (2016). Nevertheless, the effectiveness and efficiency of dialoguing as post-conflict rehabilitative mechanism ought to be enhanced by the active cooperation and collaboration with the state (Moyo 1993).

Documentation

Documentation mechanisms have been largely monopolized by the CCJP as far as post Gukurahundi scenarios are post-conflict processes are concerned. According to Lederach (1997), documentation strategies are assigned to middle-track actors in peacebuilding, who constitute academics who are bound to be instrumental in documentation processes. In the same vein, Lederach (1997) justifies the inclusion of religious leaders in CSO initiatives. In this case, CCJP is justified on religious grounds for pioneering documentation processes; nevertheless, one may critique this mechanism for adopting a top-down approach, as there is no way local ownership can be initiated from grassroots level. From a Lederachian perspective, this mechanism has the propensity to prevent the recurrence of conflict through awareness creation as well as capacity building.

Conflict Prevention, Resolution, and Transformation Mechanisms

ECLF cited the utilization of conflict prevention, resolution, and transformation mechanisms as a post-conflict rehabilitation mechanism's most effective tools in rebuilding divided societies. In the light of this assertion, one should be cognizant of the fact that the three above mentioned aspects all contribute to peace building, thus in line with Ghali's (1992) postulation that post-conflict peacebuilding should aim to reduce hostile perceptions and avoid re-emergence of renewed hostilities. With reference to ECLF initiatives, one is justified to state that this mechanism is all encompassing, as it entails the first-level operating in tandem with the second level so as to effectively mend relationships, engineer preventative measures, and so forth as stipulated in the Lederachian view. Moreover, in post-conflict rehabilitation, Orjuela (2003) stresses that the incorporation of peace-education initiatives will ultimately equip individuals with necessary conflict resolution and transformation skills to ensure the sustainability of the peace process. Hence, to ensure effective conflict prevention, resolution, and transformation in a post-conflict society, peace education ought to be the epicenter of all operations. Therefore, organizations aimed at transforming minds and deconstructing violent tendencies, such as ECLF, are challenged to fully utilize peace-education strategies in their initiatives.

Having explored the faith-based post-conflict operations, one can easily align these to the Lederachian perspective (1997), as the faith-based initiatives explored above lay in the second strata of the peacebuilding pyramid. Therefore, this suggests that faith-based actors directly interact with the grassroots so as to solidify their initiatives. In the same vein, these faith-based institutions have managed to directly and indirectly influence the elite, as far as policy formulation and implementation are concerned. Hence, the institutions ought to speak truth to power. Such organizations include ECLF and Habakkuk trust, who have attempted collaborative efforts with the government towards post-conflict processes. Despite their efforts being fruitless, these CSOs, especially faith-based institutions, ought to be applauded for their conformity to the Lederachian perspective, as they have dual influence on both the State and the broad base.

Pressure Groups/Non-Faith Based Institution Initiatives

Pressure groups or non-faith based institutions ought to be afforded recognition in the field of post-conflict rehabilitation, as they build their momentum from social sentiments thus utilizing social sentiments as a mobilization tool. Despite faith-based initiatives being preferred and arguably considered more effective, non-faith based institutions conform to the Merkel and Lauth model and the Lederachian perspective. As a result of their distinct role in war torn societies, pressure groups are classified as non-governmental organizations, as they pioneer all dimensions of human security, thus rehabilitating victims of war as well as strengthening broken societies (Weker & Ahmed, 2007).

Memorialization

As deduced from the research findings purposed for this paper, pressure groups such as IBhethshu Lika Zulu have been in the forefront of memorialization strategies. In a bid to justify the dominance

of this strategy, Guzura and Dube (2016) posit that memorialization is the jugular vein of post-conflict peacebuilding, thus outlining the need to appreciate the employment of memorialization techniques within the post-Gukurahundi context. Nevertheless, these initiatives have been met with stern resistance from state authorities such that their efficiency has been gravely affected. To cement this assertion of state interference, Atobi (2010) lays the foundation for the understanding of strenuous state-CSO relations, which explains the disruption of these CSO-led memorial initiatives. Moreover, lack of local ownership of these memorialization initiatives has contributed to the ineffectiveness of this particular peacebuilding panacea. In the light of this assertion, Lederach (1997) opines that post-conflict initiatives in all their facets ought to adopt a bottom-up approach, such that the initiative will be wholly acceptable as well as sustainable. Grappling with this school of thought, one is compelled to state that as far as memorialization is concerned, IBhetshu Lika Zulu failed conform to the Lederachian perspective, which might have ultimately contributed to the ineffectiveness of the strategy. Some community members in the remote location of Bulawayo denounced this strategy and expressed their discontent with its implementation. Hence, it is on these bases that the strategy has been tried and tested in its quest for post-conflict rehabilitation within the context of Gukurahundi

Reburials

Marshall (1999) posits that in post-conflict rehabilitation, the ultimate goal should be to restore sanity, give closure to whomever it is due, and bring about victim-offender and community justice. Therefore, the employment of reburial mechanisms can be argued as a solution, which has the capacity to weave together a divided society plagued by amnesia of the past. This mechanism has been advocated for by various pressure groups as a viable means of healing fractured societies. The Mthwakazi Republic party has financed and actively advocated for reburial exercises in the remote area of Matobo. Nevertheless, the CSO's means-to-an-end approach has been condemned by other CSOs as unprocedural, as the haphazard reburials will destroy the hope of relatives recovering their missing relatives. Despite this hurdle, this stance ought to be appreciated in the quest for post-conflict rehabilitation in the Gukurahundi context. Nevertheless, CSOs have met resistance in their reburial initiatives and advocacy. In this context, Vice President Mphoko was quoted in *Bulawayo 24 News*, stating: "We cannot go to mass graves and start digging; it is not in our African Culture" ("Mphoko on Gukurahundi Climbdown," par. 5). Given this remark, one might question whether the genocidal killings were African in the first place. In an affirming stance, the Mthwakazi Republic Party is rooted in the notion that reburials are the sole antidote to the ever-present Gukurahundi tensions, as this move will afford relatives of the Gukurahundi victims a chance to properly pay respect to their relatives and this will positively constitute a step towards justice.

Community Response of CSO Societal Post Conflict Rehabilitation

For any grassroots initiative to be a success, local ownership ultimately becomes the cornerstone of the entire operation. Hence, it is of paramount importance to consider societal/community response and acceptance of these post-Gukurahundi initiatives. As such, the consideration of

community or grassroots response ultimately becomes the lifeline of this paper, as it aligns itself with the Lederachian perspective of prioritizing the broad base in a bid to scrutinize whether CSO initiatives employed the bottom-up approach. Hence, one may attribute this aspect to the compromised mandate of the CSOs, such that there has been an ultimate mismatch between its operations and societal expectations. Chambers and Kopstein (2001) posit that one of the ultimate drawbacks in CSO effectiveness is the notion of the “bad civil society” or the “uncivil civil society,” which inflicts more harm than good on the grassroots; hence, this explains the reason CSO initiatives have ultimately lost favor in the eyes of the society.

Moreover, the majority of community members, whether CSO beneficiaries or not, still question the credibility of post-conflict processes due to the top-down approach adopted by some CSOs, especially those pursuing governmental agendas at the expense of post-conflict victims. This has hastened a lack of local ownership of these initiatives, as they do not address the felt needs of the affected communities. By the same token, this ultimately negatively impacts the effectiveness of CSO initiatives, as the individuals to whom the initiatives are targeted do not wholly accept them. One may attribute this to CSOs adopting a top-down approach, contradicting Lederach (1997), who advocates for synergies between and among tracks of the pyramid such that the idea of post-conflict rehabilitation is wholly appreciated. As such, one can attribute this hurdle to the inability of responsible CSOs to conduct a needs assessment of the target group prior to the implementation of these post conflict strategies. This line of thought is evidenced by the individual’s need of economic and financial assistance, as opposed to the usual services rendered by CSOs such as memorialization, dialoguing, and so forth.

Be that as it may, to ensure that CSO initiatives reach their full potential and yield desired results, CSOs must conduct needs assessments in affected communities to implement strategies that are acceptable and tangible to the community to better the lives of victims and survivor. One may then argue that the CSOs have been straying from the Lederachian perspective, as CSOs have been operating in isolation instead of actively collaborating with the grassroots to ensure that initiatives are contextual and relevant to the societies to which they are applied.

State-Civil Society Relations in Post-Conflict Societal Rehabilitation

State-CSO relations is an area that is still being tinkered with by scholars and experts in the field. However, Barnes (2006) three Cs (cooperation, co-optation, and confrontation) have typified the state-CSO relations. However, State-CSO relations within this context have been more confrontational than complementary, as resistance from the state has been encountered from all angles. CSOs operating within the context of Gukurahundi have experienced political meddling, thus bringing this aspect is subject to scrutiny. From an academic point of view, one is compelled to posit that CSOs should be a separate entity of the State, thus suggesting the independence of CSOs from government influence (Moyo, 1993). Nevertheless, various CSOs have engaged in confrontational relationships with the State such that their activities are compromised, ultimately

jeopardizing the post-conflict processes. IBhetshu Lika Zulu, for example, has been the object of ridicule by authorities, as their prayer marches and commemorations were ruthlessly and repeatedly dispersed by members of the uniformed forces. Hence, it is indisputable that the State has been in the forefront of disrupting CSO-led post-conflict initiatives. Atobi (2010) states that post-conflict initiatives are compromised by state interference, as the State will be infringing in the domain of the Civil Society. Hence, it is of essence to consider how a vast number of CSO spearheaded initiatives have been a causality of political prestige.

ECLF cited how the co-optation of FBOs has compromised issues of human security. The credibility of these institutions is being questioned, as they no longer represent the interests or serve as the voice of the people; instead, they are vessels of repressive governments. CSOs have fallen into the trap of co-optation, as they are frequently enticed by government incentives, thus motivating FBOs to abandon their God-given mandate for material benefits at the expense of conflict torn societies. In cementing this notion, Chambers and Kopstein (2001) posit the notion of a bad or “uncivil civil society” which has jeopardized CSO operations within the post-conflict context as evidenced in the findings.

Habakkuk Trust outlined how its operations have been hindered by government interference. Members of the uniformed forces had the tendency of interfering with the Habakkuk Trust organized gatherings. In an attempted truth telling mechanism, government officials sabotaged the whole operation, such that it was a failure. Habakkuk Trust outlined how an unofficial ban was issued against them barring them from operating in some areas of Matabeleland. Hence, restrained State-CSO relations have ultimately engulfed CSO operations. Similarly, Grace to Heal stated that most of its operations have been hindered by the government, as most of the perpetrators are in the realms of power and government. Due to vested interests, these political officials will ultimately act as spoilers to post-conflict processes in the context of Gukurahundi. ECLF claimed that it is currently engaged in conflictual relations with the government due to its ability to speak truth power on Gukurahundi issues. Strenuous State-CSO relations are the main hurdle hindering the successful implementation of CSO initiatives, such that the majority of the organizations have fallen victim to political challenges.

In a bid to further cement the notion of strenuous state-CSO relations, it was recently noted by *Bulawayo 24 News*, as IBhetshu Lika Zulu stated that the Vice president (representing the arm of the government) is “the wrong person to bring closure about the Gukurahundi issue, as he is approaching the issue with dirty hands,” thereby concluding that in this context the “perpetrator cannot prescribe the solution.” Thus, this argument cements the incompatibility between the State and civil society, serving as evidence that the state and CSO will never be engaged in a collaborative relationship for a greater good.

Furthermore, despite civil society being an entity separate from the State, it should collaborate with the State or government in rehabilitating post-conflict societies. Despite the confrontational

and conflictual relations between the state and civil society, their efforts ought to be complimentary in achieving a desired outcome, i.e. prevention of the recurrence of conflict as well as achievement of sustainable peace. Though they may be separate entities, one institution cannot be independent of the other, such that in order to influence adoption of new policy frameworks the CSO needs the state, and the state needs the civil society due to its proximity to the grassroots. Hence, it is commendable for CSOs to collaborate with the state for a greater good.

Way Forward

Aligning the views of the author to the Lederachian perspective, it is imperative to note that all post-Gukurahundi initiatives should adopt a bottom-up approach while prioritizing the victims and affected societies (Lederach, 1997). This approach would ensure that the felt needs of victims are well addressed, thereby laying a firm foundation for the sustainability of these initiatives. The future and sustenance of CSO pioneered peacebuilding initiatives lies with cultivating healthy CSO-State relations. As separate entities, the State and CSOs should recognize and respect the mandate and domain of the other institution (Moyo, 1993). Hence, instead of the State and CSOs being at loggerheads, there should be synergies and cooperation between the two institutions to ensure a proper flow and implementation of initiatives.

Conclusion

In summation, this paper explores CSO post-conflict rehabilitation initiatives within the context of Gukurahundi in their quest for social cohesion and durable peace. The post-conflict initiatives in question were grassroots centered; hence, one could argue that the CSOs were pioneering a bottom-up approach of post-conflict peacebuilding advocated by Lederach (1997) in his peacebuilding pyramid. Moreover, the majority of CSOs that effectively pioneered post-Gukurahundi initiatives were faith-based organizations, as compared to their non-faith based counterparts. However, most of these FBOs became quasi-CSOs, as they were co-opted by the repressive government, thereby compromising the entire rehabilitation effort and eroding their own integrity in the process. Related findings exposed that the State was ultimately a sworn enemy to any Gukurahundi-oriented initiative, hence providing a tangible reason for the underperformance of respective CSOs within the given context. Furthermore, the inefficiency of some CSOs is largely attributed to their inability to conform to the Lederachian framework. In conclusion, it is of essence for CSOs to appreciate and conform to the Lederachian perspective of peacebuilding in post-Gukurahundi Zimbabwe. As a blanket assessment of the CSO initiatives, one can hazard that in order for these CSOs to achieve large-scale effectiveness, CSOs should not centralize their operations but should nationalize their efforts to increase the scope of their effectiveness.

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